

Guidelines for Victim-Safety During Mediation of Domestic Violence

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Abstract

This paper explores the intricacies of domestic violence (DV) and the role of mediation as a tool for conflict resolution, emphasizing the need for a safe environment for victims during the mediation process. It begins by outlining the legal framework in South Africa, highlighting the Domestic Violence Act of 1998 and the relevance of mediation under Rule 41A. The discussion then shifts to the root causes of domestic violence, with particular attention to power imbalances, the psychological profiles of abusers, and the cyclical nature of abuse. Drawing from the theory of cyclic abuse (Walker, 1970), the paper underscores how abusers manipulate victims through phases of tension, acting out, apologies, and calm, thereby perpetuating a cycle that makes it difficult for victims to break free.

The paper addresses the challenges of mediation in domestic violence cases, particularly the power dynamics and the potential for manipulation by the abuser. Specific mediation approaches, including evaluative, facilitative, transformative, and narrative mediation, are discussed with a focus on how each approach can aid in empowering the victim and ensuring their safety. The importance of pre-mediation screening and a trauma-informed approach is highlighted as essential steps in ensuring a fair and balanced process. Finally, the paper recommends the use of shuttle mediation, the inclusion of advocates or support persons, and ongoing safety planning to protect the victim from further harm.

Overall, the paper advocates for a comprehensive mediation process that addresses the emotional and psychological vulnerabilities of victims while also ensuring legal protections are in place to prevent further victimization.

Keywords

Domestic Violence, Mediation, Trauma-Informed, Power Imbalance, Cycle of Abuse, Cluster B Personality Disorders, South Africa, Domestic Violence Act 116 of 1998, Rule 41A.

1. Introduction

In South Africa, domestic violence cases are typically handled under the Domestic Violence Act (116 of 1998), which provides protection orders and legal remedies for victims of abuse (1). While the Uniform Rule (Rule 41A) acknowledge mediation as an alternative dispute resolution (ADR) instrument, the tool is intended to provide both parties the opportunity to settle their disputes outside court (2). However, mediators for domestic violence must be adequately trained to secure competence to handle sensitive matters relating to power dynamics and manipulation that commonly characterise domestic violence (3). This paper seeks to advance ways in which mediation process prevents extending victimisation. This is particularly important given the dynamic nature of domestic violence. That requires a comprehensive approach and commitment to address the root cause of each case. Effective mediation necessitate to treat each case as unique and be flexible to customise mitigation that are particularly informed by pre-mediation screening.

Image 1: Domestic Violence Awareness Month (October). This image highlights the global campaign for Domestic Violence Awareness Month, observed in October. The goal is to raise awareness about domestic violence and promote actions to prevent it (credit: <https://za.pinterest.com/mdz lady/>).

The proclamation of Domestic Violence Awareness Month (DVAM) came in the wake of increasing activism in the 1970s and 1980s by grassroots organizations, shelters, and advocates working to combat violence in the home. The movement gained traction as more survivors shared their stories, and advocates highlighted the need for systemic support, legal reforms, and public awareness to protect victims. DVAM is observed every October in many countries, particularly in the United States, as a way to raise awareness and promote action to prevent and address domestic violence. It was first proclaimed in October 1987 as a way to unite advocates across the country in their efforts to end violence against women, men, and children. The proclamation of DVAM was spearheaded by the National Coalition Against Domestic Violence (NCADV), an organization that was instrumental in advocating for nationwide recognition of the need to address domestic violence as a public health and societal issue. In 1989, the U.S. Congress officially recognized October as Domestic Violence Awareness Month, further solidifying its significance. The month now serves as a focal point for community organizations, legal systems, and policymakers to coordinate educational events, legislative advocacy, and support for survivors. It also highlights the ongoing need to

create safer environments and provide resources for individuals affected by domestic violence. Since its inception, DVAM has grown to become a global movement, with countries around the world hosting similar awareness campaigns to prevent intimate partner violence, supporting victims, and advocating for stronger legal protections. The month encourages everyone to take an active role in ending domestic violence through education, prevention, and by fostering a culture of respect and non-violence.

However, In South Africa, Domestic Violence commonly stems from Gender-Based Violence (GBV) phenomenon. GBV Awareness Month in South Africa is observed during the 16 Days of Activism for No Violence Against Women and Children Campaign, which runs from November 25 to December 10 each year. The campaign begins on International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women (November 25) and concludes on Human Rights Day (December 10). This period is dedicated to raising awareness, mobilizing communities, and advocating for the prevention of all forms of violence against women and children. The 16 Days of Activism campaign is also a global initiative, and in South Africa, it has become a key part of the country's efforts to address the high levels of GBV. The South African government, civil society organizations, and various other stakeholders use this period to spotlight the issue and promote action toward ending gender-based violence and supporting survivors. It is also important note that in South Africa, the month of October is dedicated to various awareness campaigns aimed at improving the well-being and safety of its citizens. Some of the key awareness programs advocated by the South African government in October include:

- **Mental Health Awareness Month:** This campaign promotes awareness about mental health issues and aims to reduce stigma and discrimination associated with mental illnesses. The government encourages the public to seek support and engage in open conversations about mental health challenges, particularly in the context of trauma caused by violence, poverty, and other social issues.
- **Breast Cancer Awareness Month:** October is also dedicated to raising awareness about breast cancer. This initiative focuses on the importance of early detection through regular screening, particularly for women over 40. The

Department of Health often collaborates with non-governmental organizations to provide education and screening services, especially in underserved communities.

- **Transport Month:** The South African government observes October as Transport Month, highlighting the role of transport in the economy and its importance for social development. The government emphasizes safety on the roads, the need for investment in infrastructure, and the promotion of public transport as a sustainable alternative to private vehicle use.
- **Social Development Initiatives:** October is also a time when the government and various agencies run campaigns focused on issues like older persons' rights and food security. These initiatives aim to create awareness of the challenges faced by vulnerable populations, such as the elderly and the poor.

These are South African government driven campaigns. Designed to reflect the country's broader commitment to promoting health, safety, and well-being. Mainly to foster national dialogue, and encouraging community involvement in addressing societal challenges. Notwithstanding, that DV is a deeply entrenched multidimensional problem that affects individuals and families from all socioeconomic backgrounds, races, genders, and cultures. All these segments are impacted by one party exerting power and/or control over another (4). The root causes of domestic violence are often complex. Their effects extend beyond the individuals directly involved. The cascading impact of DV reach as far as community and generations. The impact is sometimes immediately and often it is gradual (5). Making it often difficult to identify its genesis and to locate its tracks.

2. Characteristics of Domestic Violence (DV)

Domestic violence manifest in various forms, including physical, isolation, control, verbal, emotional, psychological, sexual, gaslighting, defamation of character, mockery, bullying, and mobbing and financial abuse. Abusers are possessive and usually deny their actions of blaming and controlling the victim. In fact research suggests that they

are insecure and suffer from untreated mental health problems, including depression and suicidal ideation (6). Making these type of abusers them particularly dangerous.

Image 2: Shows types of domestic abuse. This diagram classifies domestic violence into various types, such as physical, emotional, psychological, sexual, and financial abuse, each having unique characteristics and impacts on the victim.

3. Characteristics of Mediation

Each form of abuse is devastating in isolation— but often inflicted in combination of more than one form of abuse. The mediation to this requires appropriate dispatching of intervention such as legal cause, therapy and economic support. The process must help victims find an environment that escapes abuse and rebuild their lives (7). The mediation process must follow the following mediation approach; evaluative mediation, facilitative mediation, transformative mediation and narrative mediation. The settlement nature of mediation is designed to afford the perpetrator an opportunity to self-reflect and self-correct. The process must prioritize victim safety and healing. The settlement must reach a point where both parties agree on what will guarantee the victim safety and healing.

4. Challenges of Mediation

Image 3: This diagram connects mental health issues and their impact on domestic violence, explaining how untreated mental health conditions contribute to abusive behaviours.

While mediation can offer a less adversarial and more flexible approach to dispute resolution, the unique dynamics of domestic violence pose significant challenges. Power imbalances, the potential of manipulation, and the absence of legal protections make it essential that mediators are thoroughly trained in trauma-informed practices and are equipped to recognize the signs of abuse. Victim safety must be prioritized at every stage, and in some cases, litigation may be a more appropriate option to ensure the victim's protection and access to justice. Given that one of the most significant challenges in DV mediation is the inherent power imbalance between the victim and the abuser. Not withholding that DV is often characterized by the abuser's need to exert control and dominance over the victim, and this dynamic does not automatically disappear in mediation (10). Victims may:

- feel intimidated or unable to express their needs freely due to fear of retaliation.
- be coerced into accepting terms that are not in their best interest.
- struggle to advocate for themselves, especially if they have been subjected to psychological manipulation or emotional abuse for an extended period [Gawie le Roux Institute of Law, South African Government](#)

4A. Manipulation by the Abuser

Abusers may use the less formal structure of mediation to manipulate the process and continue exerting control over the victim. This can include tactics like (11):

- Making the victim question their reality or perceptions (Gaslighting) .
- The abuser may downplay the seriousness of their actions or shift blame onto the victim (Minimizing or denying the abuse).
- Using guilt, remorse, or false promises to manipulate the victim into compromising their safety or needs (Emotional blackmail)

Image 4: This diagram outlines the power imbalances between abusers and victims, showing how control, coercion, and intimidation play roles in maintaining the abusive relationship.

4B. Lack of Legal Protections

Unlike court proceedings, mediation does not automatically provide legal protections such as restraining orders or emergency protection measures. This can be particularly dangerous for victims of domestic violence, as they may lack the legal safeguards that would protect them from further harm during or after the mediation process. Victims may still need to pursue court-issued protection orders alongside mediation to ensure their safety (12).

4C Victim Safety

Ensuring the victim's physical and emotional safety throughout the mediation process is another major challenge. Without appropriate safeguards, mediation can expose the victim to further psychological or emotional harm. Even in controlled environments, the abuser's presence can be intimidating, and the victim may feel unsafe or pressured to agree to terms they would not otherwise accept (13). Strategies like shuttle mediation (where parties are in separate rooms) are often used to mitigate this risk, but they do not eliminate the underlying fear and intimidation completely.

4D. Trauma and Emotional Vulnerability

Victims of domestic violence often suffer from trauma, which may manifest as anxiety, PTSD, or learned helplessness. These psychological factors can affect the victim's ability to fully participate in mediation and make sound decisions (14). Mediators must be trained to recognize and accommodate these emotional and psychological vulnerabilities, but even with such training, the trauma can significantly hinder the mediation process.

4E. Challenges with Voluntary Participation

Mediation is typically a voluntary process, which means both parties must agree to participate. In cases of domestic violence, the victim may feel pressured to agree to mediation, either by the abuser or by external factors such as family or legal advice. This can undermine the principle of true voluntary participation, as the victim may feel that they have no other option but to mediate (15)

4F. Inability to Address Legal Complexities

Mediation focuses on collaborative solutions, but it may not be the appropriate forum for resolving certain legal issues that arise in domestic violence cases, such as: Courts may need to intervene to ensure the safety of children, particularly when an abuser seeks access to them (Child custody and visitation); And in cases involving financial abuse, the victim may require legal remedies that mediation cannot provide without legal backing (Financial settlements) (16).

4G. Risk of Retaliation

Even after mediation has ended, there is a risk that the abuser will continue to retaliate against the victim, especially if the outcome of the mediation is not favourable to them. Stalking, harassment, or even physical violence may occur post-mediation, particularly if the victim has tried to assert their rights or boundaries during the process (17). This underscores the need for ongoing safety planning during and after mediation.

4H. Difficulty in Enforcing Agreements

Unlike court orders, agreements made in mediation are not automatically enforceable unless they are formalized in a legal document or presented to a court for approval. If the abuser chooses to ignore the agreement, the victim may have little recourse without returning to the legal system. This can be particularly problematic when dealing with financial support, property division, or child custody arrangements (8,9).

5. Dynamics of DV Mediation

Huss define the nature of domestic violence as any action of violence perpetrated within the context of significant interpersonal relationship (18). Domestic violence could include violence between a husband and a wife, a girlfriend and boyfriend, or gay or lesbian partners (19). It could be violence between parents and children, adult children

and elderly parents, or could be between siblings. As domestic violence cases increasingly enter the legal system, the harmful effects on victims' physical and emotional well-being—whether within families or other environments—are becoming more evident. While both men and women can initiate violent behaviour, the violence perpetrated by women tends to occur less frequently and results in less severe consequences compared to violence by men.

Research by Straus and Gelles, through the National Family Violence Survey, revealed that women are six times more likely to suffer injuries than men (20). Globally, between 10% and 50% of women report having been physically assaulted by an intimate partner at some point in their lives. Moreover, estimates suggest that up to one-third of women experience domestic violence during their lifetime. Annually, approximately four million women only in USA are assaulted by a domestic partner (21).

5A. Evaluative Mediation of Abuse Victim

A common pattern of domestic abuse, especially between intimate partners, is that the perpetrator alternates between violent, abusive and apologetic behaviour with apparently heartfelt promises to change and that the abuser could be very pleasant most of the time. Walker (1970, 1984, 1999) developed (22, 23), on the basis of social cycle theory and Seligman's phenomenon of learned helplessness, the theory of cyclic abuse with a hypothesis that abusive relationships, once established, are characterized by a predictable repetitious pattern of abuse. She suggested that sustained periods of living in such a cycle may lead victim to learned helplessness. Abuse Cycle is known also as a Battered Women Syndrome which consists of these symptoms: re-experiencing the battering as if it were recurring even when it is not; attempts to avoid the psychological impact of battering by avoiding activities, people, and emotions; hyper arousal or hyper vigilance; disrupted interpersonal relationships; body image distortion or other somatic concerns; sexuality and intimacy issues (24).

5B Evaluative Mediation of Abuse Stages

Abuse is rarely constant but alternates between four stages: i) period of tension building (tension starts and steadily builds, abuser starts to get angry, communication breaks down, victim feels the need to concede to the abuser, tension becomes too much, victim feels uneasy); ii) acting out period (any type of abuse occurs); iii) the honeymoon period (abuser apologizes for abuse, some beg forgiveness or show sorrows, abuser may promise it will never happen again, blames victim for provoking the abuse or denies abuse occurred, minimizing); iv) the calm period (abuse stops, abuser acts like the abuse never happened, promises made during honeymoon stage may be met, abuser may give gifts to victim, victim believes or wants to believe that the abuse is over or that the abuser will change) (25).

Image 5: This image highlights common challenges faced during mediation in domestic violence cases, such as power imbalances, manipulation by the abuser, lack of legal protections, and ensuring the victim’s safety. CREDIT: WHO

In fact, such a behaviour pattern explains why for the most victims it is so difficult to break their exhausting relationship. Due to perpetrator's acts of apologies and loving gestures between the episodes of abuse, they are ready to believe that partner's violent and abusive practice will really never appear again. But on the other hand, it is also not so simple if a battered woman decides to stop her relationship. Research data pointed out that leaving the relation with the partner often does not stop the abuse. Many perpetrators continue to harass, stalk, and harm the victim long after she has left him, sometimes even resulting in someone's death. In one U.S. study, 70 per cent of reported injuries from domestic violence occurred after the separation of couple (25).

5C. Abuser Profile For Transformative Mediation

Profile of an abuser correlate with the Cluster B personality disorders: Anti-Social Personality (a pervasive pattern of disregard for and violation of the rights of others, lack of empathy), Borderline Personality (a pervasive pattern of instability in relationships, self-image, identity, behaviour and affects often leading to self-harm and impulsivity), and Narcissistic Personality (a pervasive pattern of grandiosity need for admiration, and a lack of empathy). These disorders display characteristics that involve grandiose delusions and a self inflated sense of importance which are critical behaviours for an abuser to have in order to maintain strict and severe control over their victim. The abuser also needs to have a very low affect and low sense of empathy so that they do not have remorse for the abuse and actions they are inflicting on their victim. All of these qualities are characteristics found on the Axis II disorders in the DSM-IV (25).

5D. Relationship Phase Evaluative Mediation

In 2008-2009, around one in four women and one in eight men aged 18 to 59 reported experiencing partner abuse. Pregnancy is particularly a high-risk period for the onset or escalation of intimate partner violence and is a leading cause of maternal mortality in countries like the SA, UK, USA, and Australia. Research by Jasinski and Kantor similarly

found that pregnancy and the end of a relationship—when a partner feels threatened by potential loss—are particularly dangerous periods for women. Although domestic violence occurs across all social and economic groups, evidence suggests a higher prevalence among marginalized populations, including those with learning disabilities. Additionally, a study by Cooper et al. highlighted that 5.6% of older couples experienced physical violence in the previous year, with the rate significantly higher among vulnerable elders, such as those dependent on caregivers, where nearly 25% reported substantial abuse (25).

6. Mediation Elements

The goal should be to assess the risk of escalating abuse, or complicating the mediation process even further. Although collaborative efforts—spanning from education, legal reform, mental health support, and economic empowerment—can address the systemic nature of domestic violence and reduce its prevalence- but this requires effective dispensary system- which is entrenched on the competency of mediators.

The mediator must be trained to demonstrate active listening, neutral facilitation, structured communication and emotional validation. Over and above the mediator must develop stakeholder matrix that makes provision of parties access to emotional and mental health support. Mediator must also make provision for ongoing interventions as that can significantly improve the chances of a successful and sustainable solution. The ultimate goal of mediation must be to foster mutual understanding among affected parties as a foundation for achieving lasting agreements and sustainable conflict resolution. Creating a safe environment for mediation in domestic violence (DV) cases is essential due to the heightened risks of power imbalances, manipulation, and emotional vulnerability of the victim. To ensure the process is not only effective but also protective of the victim's well-being, mediators and involved professionals must implement the following strategies:

6A. Pre-Mediation Screening and Assessment

Before engaging in mediation, it is crucial to conduct pre-mediation screening to assess the dynamics of the relationship, including the history of abuse and potential for future harm. This screening helps determine if mediation is appropriate, given the risk factors involved in domestic violence cases. Screening can reveal whether the abuser exhibits traits associated with Cluster B personality disorders (e.g., Antisocial Personality Disorder or Narcissistic Personality Disorder) and whether power imbalances are likely to influence the mediation process.

- **Risk Assessment:** Tools such as the Danger Assessment or Abuse Screening Protocols can be used to gauge the level of risk to the victim's safety, especially in high-conflict or volatile relationships.
- **Assess Power Dynamics:** Pre-mediation assessments can also help identify power imbalances and whether the abuser is likely to manipulate the mediation process to control the victim further.

6B. Trauma-Informed Approach

Mediators should adopt a trauma-informed approach, which emphasizes understanding the impact of domestic violence on the victim and ensures that the mediation process is sensitive to the victim's emotional and psychological state. Trauma Sensitivity Mediators need to recognize that victims of domestic violence often suffer from anxiety, PTSD, or learned helplessness (as theorized by Lenore Walker). This requires mediators to avoid triggering the victim and to foster an environment of emotional safety. The mediator should focus on empowering the victim, giving them the tools and support to voice their needs and concerns without fear of retaliation from the abuser. Mediators must provide emotional validation and ensure that the victim feels respected and heard.

6C. Shuttle Mediation

In cases where there is a high risk of intimidation or manipulation, shuttle mediation is a safer alternative to traditional face-to-face mediation. This involves keeping the parties in separate rooms and having the mediator move between them to facilitate negotiations. Shuttle mediation helps:

- **Reduce Intimidation:** By keeping the victim physically separated from the abuser, shuttle mediation minimizes the risk of intimidation or psychological manipulation.
- **Create Emotional Safety:** The victim can express their concerns freely without fear of immediate retaliation or pressure from the abuser.

6D. Presence of an Advocate or Support Person

Allowing the victim to have a support person or advocate present during the mediation process provides emotional reassurance and helps balance power dynamics. A support person can be:

- **An Advocate:** A legal advocate who ensures that the victim understands their rights and helps them articulate their needs during mediation.
- **Emotional Support:** A trusted friend, family member, or social worker who provides emotional support during the mediation process.

6E. Confidentiality and Safety Planning

Ensuring confidentiality throughout the mediation process is essential to protect the victim from further harm. Mediators must ensure that:

- **All Discussions are Confidential:** The victim's concerns and statements should not be shared with the abuser unless explicitly agreed upon by the victim.

- **Safety Plans are in Place:** In collaboration with the victim, mediators should develop a safety plan for post-mediation, ensuring that the victim has access to legal protections such as restraining orders, safe housing, and contact with law enforcement if necessary.

6F. Focus on Practical Outcomes

Mediators should focus on crafting practical and realistic solutions that prioritize the victim's safety and well-being. This includes ensuring that any agreements made during mediation address:

- **Safety and Boundaries:** Agreements about no-contact orders, safe visitation arrangements for children, and other protective measures that minimize the risk of further harm.
- **Financial Independence:** Where applicable, ensuring that the victim has access to financial resources or support that will help them maintain independence from the abuser .

6G. Monitor for Signs of Manipulation

Given that abusers often exhibit manipulative tendencies (e.g., gaslighting, emotional blackmail), mediators must be vigilant and trained to recognize these tactics. Warning signs of manipulation might include the abuser minimizing the abuse, shifting blame onto the victim, or making promises they are unlikely to keep.

- If manipulation is detected, mediators should intervene to redirect the conversation or, if necessary, halt the mediation to protect the victim's well-being (Intervene When Necessary).

6H. Regular Check-Ins

Throughout the mediation process, mediators should conduct regular check-ins with the victim to ensure they feel safe and are not experiencing undue pressure from the abuser. This helps to:

- Ensuring that the victim is not being coerced into making decisions that jeopardize their safety or well-being (Gauge the Victim's Comfort Level).
- If the victim feels unsafe or pressured, the mediator can adjust the approach, such as moving to shuttle mediation or involving legal counsel (Adjust the Process as Needed).

Creating a safe environment for mediation in domestic violence cases requires careful consideration of the power dynamics and emotional vulnerabilities present in the relationship. By implementing trauma-informed practices, utilizing shuttle mediation, ensuring the presence of support persons, and maintaining strict confidentiality, mediators can help protect the victim and facilitate a fair and just resolution. These strategies not only prioritize the victim's safety but also empower them to take control of the process, ensuring that the mediation remains an effective and non-adversarial method of resolving disputes.

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